

Preparing Nuclear Data for Adjoint Monte Carlo Calculations

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ABSTRACT

Radiation shielding applications related to reactor design typically involve situations where the source region (the core) is much larger than the detector region (a dosimeter or an operator). In such cases, the efficiency of Monte Carlo simulation might be significantly increased by solving the adjoint transport equation: adjoint particles are born from the detector, undergo adjoint ('reversed') flights and collisions, and accumulate their tallies in the source region. Sampling the adjoint collision events demands in particular the preparation of adjoint nuclear data. In this work, we propose a general method able to handle the diversity of nuclear reactions available in modern nuclear data libraries, in view of implementing these adjoint sampling schemes in TRIPOLI-5[®]. We validate this strategy based on a relevant continuous-energy benchmark configuration involving mixtures of heavy and light nuclides, and we compare our results to those obtained by the standard forward Monte Carlo simulation.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Adjoint transport, Nuclear data, Neutron

1. INTRODUCTION

In nuclear engineering problems, one is often called to consider radiation shielding calculations where the 'detector' region (be that an operator or a dosimeter) is much smaller than the 'source' region, which may consist of the full reactor core or a cluster of fuel assemblies. In such situation, evaluating the dose via Monte Carlo methods can be extremely challenging, as very few particles will contribute to the detector response. By the reciprocity theorem, the sought response can be equivalently obtained by solving the adjoint transport equation [1]. The Monte Carlo algorithm for "solving" the adjoint transport equation implies sampling histories of fictitious adjoint particles (often called 'adjunctons') that are born in the detector region, undergo adjoint flights and collisions, and accumulate their tallies in the source region; for a thorough discussion, see e.g. Ref. [2]. Due to the relative sizes of the source and the detector, simulating adjoint transport would, in theory, yield a much higher number of contributing histories and thus a more efficient calculation. Adjoint Monte Carlo methods were developed in the 1970s [1,3], and still are a topic of active research [2,4].

In view of implementing this method in CEA's next generation Monte Carlo code TRIPOLI-5[®] [5], in a previous work we have provided a general theoretical framework for the sampling strategies required to address adjoint transport problems [2]. In this paper, we focus on the preparation of the nuclear data in the free-gas range (i.e. we neglect the thermal range and the unresolved resonance range for the moment) for the reverse sampling of collision events, and sketch a broad strategy capable of handling the wide variety of nuclear reactions present in modern nuclear data libraries.

The manuscript is organized as follows. In Section 2, we will briefly recall the theoretical basis underlying the reciprocity theorem and the simulation of adjoint histories. In Section 3, we will then present a general method to handle arbitrary reaction channels, and derive optimized strategies to sample specific reactions. In Section 4, we will focus on the discretization algorithms that underlie the preparation process. Finally, in Section 5 we will apply the proposed process to produce adjoint nuclear data and to run importance calculations on benchmark configurations.

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2. THE ADJOINT TRANSPORT EQUATION

In fixed-source time-independent problems, neutrons emerge from the source S and undergo successive flight and collision events. The collision density ψ describes the expected number of collision events at point $P = (\vec{r}, E, \vec{\Omega})$ in phase space, and the emission density χ describes the expected number of emitted neutrons at P . The Boltzmann transport equation for the collision density reads

$$\psi = \mathbb{T}\mathbb{C}\psi + \mathbb{T}S, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbb{T} is the flight operator and \mathbb{C} is the collision operator [1]. The sought response R (typically a dose or a reaction rate) can be expressed in terms of the collision density ψ as $R = \langle \psi, \eta_\psi \rangle$, where η_ψ is the collision-based response function, and brackets denote integration over the phase space.

The adjoint emission density χ^\dagger corresponds to the neutron importance function, i.e. the expected contribution to the response function of a neutron being emitted at point P [1]. The quantity $\chi^\dagger(P)$ satisfies the adjoint Boltzmann equation

$$\chi^\dagger = \mathbb{T}^\dagger \mathbb{C}^\dagger \chi^\dagger + \mathbb{T}^\dagger \eta_\psi, \quad (2)$$

where the \mathbb{T}^\dagger is the adjoint flight operator and \mathbb{C}^\dagger the adjoint collision operator [1]. The elegant reciprocity theorem states that

$$R = \langle \psi, \eta_\psi \rangle = \langle S, \chi^\dagger \rangle, \quad (3)$$

which means that any response R that can be obtained by solving the transport equation can be equivalently obtained by solving the adjoint transport equation [1,2].

In the standard Monte Carlo approach to solve a direct transport problem, neutrons are sampled from the source S , successive flights and collisions are then sampled according to \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{C} , respectively, and the tally for the response R is accumulated at each collision event by evaluating η_ψ . Equations (2) and (3) state that R can be also estimated by running an 'adjoint' Monte Carlo game where adjoint particles are born from the response function η_ψ (which becomes the adjoint source), undergo adjoint flight and collision events according to \mathbb{T}^\dagger and \mathbb{C}^\dagger , respectively, and the tally for the response is accumulated at each adjoint collision event by evaluating S (which becomes the adjoint response function) [1].

2.1. Sampling the Adjoint Collision Event

The collision kernel $C(P \rightarrow P')$ associated to the operator \mathbb{C} describes the expected number of neutrons exiting a collision around point P' for a neutron entering the collision at point P . It is usually decomposed as:

$$C(P \rightarrow P') = \sum_i \frac{N_i(\vec{r})\sigma_{i,t}(E)}{\Sigma_t(\vec{r}, E)} \times \sum_j \frac{\sigma_{i,j}(E)}{\sigma_{i,t}(E)} \times \nu_{i,j}(E) f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E', \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\Omega}'), \quad (4)$$

where N_i is the concentration of nuclide i in the mixture, $\sigma_{i,j}$ is the microscopic cross section of reaction j on nuclide i , $\nu_{i,j}$ is the average multiplicity of channel $\{i, j\}$, and $f_{i,j}$ is the distribution law of outgoing neutrons from channel $\{i, j\}$. Furthermore, $\sigma_{i,t} = \sum_j \sigma_{i,j}$ is the total microscopic cross section of nuclide i , and $\Sigma_t = \sum_i N_i \sigma_{i,t}$ is the total macroscopic cross section. In the Monte Carlo approach, the first term in the RHS of Equation (4) (a normalized probability) is used to sample the nuclide i on which the collision occurs; then, the second term (also a normalized probability) is used to sample the reaction channel j . The average multiplicity $\nu_{i,j}$ is taken into account by creating multiple outgoing neutrons, whose coordinates are sampled according to the normalized $f_{i,j}$, or by using the average multiplicity as a weight multiplier.

The adjoint collision kernel $C^\dagger(P' \rightarrow P)$ associated to the operator C^\dagger can be dealt with using a similar strategy [1,2]. Similarly to Ref. [3], we introduce arbitrary (positive) adjoint cross sections $\sigma_{i,j}^\dagger$, adjoint distribution laws $f_{i,j}^\dagger$ and adjoint multiplicities $v_{i,j}^\dagger$, and we decompose the adjoint collision kernel as:

$$C^\dagger(P' \rightarrow P) = \sum_i \frac{N_i(\vec{r})\sigma_{i,t}^\dagger(P')}{\Sigma_t^\dagger(P')} \times \sum_j \frac{\sigma_{i,j}^\dagger(P')}{\sigma_{i,t}^\dagger(P')} \times v_{i,j}^\dagger(P', P) f_{i,j}^\dagger(P' \rightarrow P). \quad (5)$$

Note that here all the arbitrary adjoint cross sections and distributions generally depend on the full phase space coordinates P . To ensure the unbiasedness of the Monte Carlo game, we require $C^\dagger(P' \rightarrow P) = C(P \rightarrow P')$. The easiest way to enforce this condition is to impose

$$\frac{N_i(\vec{r})\sigma_{i,j}(E)}{\Sigma_t(\vec{r}, E)} v_{i,j}(E) f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E', \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\Omega}') = \frac{N_i(\vec{r})\sigma_{i,j}^\dagger(P')}{\Sigma_t^\dagger(P')} v_{i,j}^\dagger(P', P) f_{i,j}^\dagger(P' \rightarrow P), \quad (6)$$

for each reaction channel $\{i, j\}$. Equation (6) rules out adjoint cross sections $\sigma_{i,j}^\dagger$ and adjoint distribution laws $f_{i,j}^\dagger$ that are null where the direct cross section and distribution law aren't. Otherwise, Equation (6) can be achieved by using $v_{i,j}^\dagger$ as a weight correction for the adjoint particle, once the nuclide i , reaction j and outgoing energies E and direction $\vec{\Omega}$ are sampled from the distributions of the adjoint game, which yields:

$$v_{i,j}^\dagger(P', P) = \frac{\Sigma_t^\dagger(P')\sigma_{i,j}(E)v_{i,j}(E) f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E', \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\Omega}')}{\Sigma_t(\vec{r}, E)\sigma_{i,j}^\dagger(P') f_{i,j}^\dagger(P' \rightarrow P)}. \quad (7)$$

3. PREPARING THE ADJOINT CROSS SECTIONS AND DISTRIBUTION LAWS

Although arbitrary $\sigma_{i,j}^\dagger$ and $f_{i,j}^\dagger$ can be used for the adjoint Monte Carlo games [2], in this work we adopt a set of definitions proposed by Hoogenboom [1], namely:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{i,j}^\dagger(E') & = \int \frac{\sigma_{i,j}(E) f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E') v_{i,j}(E)}{E} dE \\ f_{i,j}^\dagger(E' \rightarrow E, \vec{\Omega}' \cdot \vec{\Omega}) & = \frac{\sigma_{i,j}(E) f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E', \vec{\Omega}' \cdot \vec{\Omega}) v_{i,j}(E)}{E \sigma_{i,j}^\dagger(E')} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In order to sample the adjoint collision event, we need to prepare the adjoint cross sections $\sigma_{i,j}^\dagger$ and distribution laws $f_{i,j}^\dagger$. The $\sigma_{i,j}^\dagger$ needs to be evaluated at any energy E' ; the $f_{i,j}^\dagger$ needs to be sampled from at any incident energy E' . Furthermore, $f_{i,j}^\dagger$ needs to be evaluated at a given outgoing energy E and deflection cosine $\vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\Omega}'$ (for any E'), in order to compute the post-collision weight correction $v_{i,j}^\dagger$ using Equation (7).

To do so, we need to evaluate Equation (8) and store the obtained values prior to calculation. This means that the actual adjoint cross-sections and distribution law that will be used in the calculation will be numerically integrated and discretized versions of Equation (8). This discrepancy will not induce a bias, as long as the weight correction defined in Equation (7) is applied using the actual discretized data (this fact was emphasized by Matteis and Simonini in Ref. 3). However, we still aim for the discretized data to be as close as possible to Equation (8) as it has been shown to have a variance reduction effect compared to other possible definitions [1,2].

3.1. The Case of General Distribution Laws

We begin by proposing a general strategy to store the *energy* component of a distribution law; this approach will be later refined for distinct reaction channels. A way of obtaining a distribution law $f_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ that we can easily sample from would be to evaluate the non-normalized energy distribution

$$\tilde{f}_{i,j}^{\dagger}(E' \rightarrow E) := \sigma_{i,j}^{\dagger}(E') f_{i,j}^{\dagger}(E' \rightarrow E) = \sigma_{i,j}(E) f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E') v_{i,j}(E) / E \quad (9)$$

at a set of well-chosen incident energies E'_k . For each E'_k , we evaluate the non-normalized density $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ at a well-chosen set of outgoing energies $E_{k,l}$. For each non-normalized density $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^{\dagger}$, we can compute the corresponding non-normalized cumulative distribution $\tilde{F}_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ at energies $E_{k,l}$ by numerically integrating between the chosen E values using the trapezoidal rule, which is exact for linear piecewise functions. Properly choosing the discretization points E'_k and $E_{k,l}$ requires careful consideration, in order to obtain sufficiently precise interpolation while avoiding prohibitive storage size. This will be performed by generic two-dimensional discretization algorithms described in Section 4.

The values of $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ at any arbitrary pair (E', E) can be evaluated by linearly interpolating twice. First, we find the two values $\{E'_k, E'_{k+1}\}$ that bracket E' ; each of these corresponds to a function of E , $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^{\dagger}(E'_k \rightarrow E)$ and $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^{\dagger}(E'_{k+1} \rightarrow E)$. We linearly interpolate these functions at E , obtaining two values; finally, we linearly interpolate (in E') between these values. The cumulative distribution $\tilde{F}_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ can be interpolated similarly, except that the interpolations in the E dimension are quadratic. To sample from a distribution at E'_k , one evaluates the norm of $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ by using the value of the cumulative distribution at $E_{k,l}$ for the maximum l . Based on the obtained norm, we can recover the normalized distribution $f_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ and sample from it via inverse transform sampling. To sample from a distribution at any arbitrary E' , we find k such that $E'_k \leq E' < E'_{k+1}$, then we sample from the distribution at E'_k with probability $p_k = (E'_{k+1} - E') / (E'_{k+1} - E'_k)$, and otherwise sample from the distribution at E'_{k+1} . This conditional sampling is equivalent to sampling from a distribution that is linearly interpolated (in E') between the distribution at E'_k and the one at E'_{k+1} . The adjoint cross section $\sigma_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ is easily evaluated at an energy E' , corresponding to the norm of $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^{\dagger}$ at E' (this can be shown by integrating Equation (9) in E to obtain Equation (8)), by getting the non-normalized cumulative for E' at E_{\max} .

Once the energy pair (E, E') is fixed, the remaining distribution of deflection cosine μ_{ℓ} is the same in direct and in adjoint transport (this can be shown by taking Equation (8) and fixing E), so one can usually sample the deflection cosine μ_{ℓ} using the direct distribution. An alternative strategy would be to enforce an isotropic distribution, at the expense of extra variance. For specific reactions (such as for elastic scattering), the deflection cosine μ_{ℓ} is imposed by the energy pair (E, E') .

The general strategy presented above requires access to $f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E')$ in the laboratory frame, while some distributions in the nuclear libraries are given in the center-of-mass frame. In such case, we change the frame before numerically integrating over μ_{ℓ} to obtain an approximation of $f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E')$, which will then be discretized.

The approach consisting in storing directly the law for (E', E) is fairly broad and can be applied to most outgoing distribution types in the ENDF format (e.g. evaporation spectrum, n -body and Kalbach-Mann distributions, etc.). However, two-dimensional discretization can be imprecise or require a lot of data points (the presence of potentially resonant cross-section $\sigma_{i,j}$ in Equation (8) can lead to difficulties). Thus, in order to reduce discretization errors (ultimately responsible for increased variance), we have derived optimized methods for key reaction channels such as elastic scattering, discrete level inelastic scattering or fission.

3.2. Elastic Scattering

In many neutron-transport problems, elastic scattering is the dominant reaction. In direct simulations, the angular distribution of elastic scattering is usually stored as a function of (E, μ_c) , μ_c being the cosine of the deflection angle in the center of mass system. The advantage is that the distribution in μ_c always spans $[-1, 1]$, whereas the distribution in E' spans from αE to E , which is a moving boundary (the boundary of the distribution in E' depends on E), making interpolation more difficult. As customary, $\alpha = (A - 1)^2 / (A + 1)^2$, where A is the mass of the nuclide in units of neutron mass. In adjoint games, we use the technique described in Section 3.1, but we store the adjoint angular distribution $g_{i,j}^+(E', \mu_c)$, defined as:

$$g_{i,j}^+(E', \mu_c) = f_{i,j}^+(E' \rightarrow E) \left| \frac{dE}{d\mu_c} \right| = \frac{2E^2 A f_{i,j}^+(E' \rightarrow E)}{E'(1+A)^2}. \quad (10)$$

The non-normalized angular distribution $\tilde{g}_{i,j}^+$ is defined using Equation (10), with the non-normalized $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^+$ instead of $f_{i,j}^+$. We obtain then the outgoing energy E and the deflection cosine in the laboratory frame using

$$\begin{cases} E = E' \times \frac{(1+A)^2}{A^2 + 2A\mu_c + 1} \\ \mu_\ell = \frac{1 + A\mu_c}{\sqrt{A^2 + 2A\mu_c + 1}} \end{cases}. \quad (11)$$

This procedure is general and holds even for anisotropic elastic scattering. However, it involves storing data in two-dimensional distributions, which might be prohibitively expensive if the data to store contains many features (e.g. resonances). From Equation (8), the distribution law $f_{i,j}^+$ depends on the cross section $\sigma_{i,j}$: for resonant nuclides, this might lead to a dramatic increase of the number of discretization points. Fortunately, a more efficient technique exists for isotropic scattering.

The energy distribution law for isotropic elastic scattering is $f_{i,j}(E \rightarrow E') = ((1 - \alpha)E)^{-1}$ (i.e. uniform) in $[\alpha E, E]$, and zero elsewhere. This formula only depends on E' via the bounds of the function, which allows pre-computing the density:

$$\tilde{h}(E) = \frac{\sigma_{i,j}(E) v_{i,j}(E)}{(1 - \alpha)E^2}, \quad (12)$$

and the associated cumulative distribution $\tilde{H}(E)$, i.e. the integral of $\tilde{h}(E)$ from E_{\min} to E . These one-dimensional functions are discretized by properly choosing a set of energies E_k at which \tilde{h} will be evaluated. Then, the cumulative distribution \tilde{H} can be numerically integrated on the points E_k ; \tilde{h} can be evaluated by linear interpolation and \tilde{H} by quadratic interpolation. In order to obtain the list of E_k values to chose, we will use the general one-dimensional discretization algorithm detailed in Section 4.

From the two one-dimensional functions, one can finally retrieve the non-normalized distribution $\tilde{f}_{i,j}^+(E' \rightarrow E)$ and the non-normalized cumulative by truncating $\tilde{h}(E)$ and $\tilde{H}^+(E)$ in $[E', E'/\alpha]$. This one-dimensional approximation can be used at energies (usually below 0.1 MeV), where cross sections are resonant and scattering is usually isotropic, whereas the full two-dimensional method of Section 3.1 can be used at higher energies.

3.3. Discrete-Level Inelastic Scattering

The treatment of discrete-level inelastic scattering is done in the same way as for elastic scattering, by adapting the relations between the deflection cosine μ_c in the center of mass frame (and μ_ℓ in the laboratory frame), the incident energy E and the outgoing energy E' . Since the distribution law $f_{i,j}$ is also uniform, although between different bounds, the isotropic approximation of the previous section

Figure 1. Adjoint distribution laws for the elastic scattering of ^{238}U . **Left.** The pre-calculated function $\tilde{h}(E)$ for the isotropic part of the energy spectrum (here for $E' < 40$ keV). The presence of the direct cross-section in Equation (8) creates visible resonances in $\tilde{h}(E)$. This function is discretized with a precision of 10%, and has approximately 15 000 points. **Right.** The two-dimensional non-normalized distribution law $\tilde{g}_{i,j}^+(E', \mu_c)$, that is used in the anisotropic part of the energy spectrum (here for $E' > 40$ keV). The transition from isotropic to anisotropic as energy E' increases is visible. This two-dimensional distribution is discretized with a precision of 20% and consists of 57 distributions in μ_c holding an average of 13 discretization points each for a total of 735 points. Distributions are plotted with a color gradient from blue to red for readability.

also works for discrete-level inelastic scattering. A thorough derivation of the relation laws between the different quantities can be found in Ref. 1.

3.4. Fission

The fission reaction also has a structure that allows avoiding two-dimensional discretization. To a good approximation, the fission neutron emission spectra $\chi_{f,i}(E')$ can be considered independent of the energy E of the entering particle. We then have:

$$f_{i,j}^+(E' \rightarrow E) = \frac{\sigma_{i,j}(E)\chi_{f,i}(E')v_{i,j}(E)/E}{\int \sigma_{i,j}(\tilde{E})\chi_{f,i}(E')v_{i,j}(\tilde{E})/\tilde{E}d\tilde{E}} = \frac{\sigma_{i,j}(E)v_{i,j}(E)/E}{\int \sigma_{i,j}(\tilde{E})v_{i,j}(\tilde{E})/\tilde{E}d\tilde{E}} \quad (13)$$

and the distribution law does not depend on entering energy. We can thus prepare the distribution law by using a one-dimensional discretization. Evaluating $a := \int \sigma_{i,j}(\tilde{E})\chi_{f,i}(E')v_{i,j}(\tilde{E})/\tilde{E}d\tilde{E}$, the adjoint cross section can be obtained via $\sigma_{i,j}^+(E') = a\chi_{f,i}(E')$. Once the energy E has been sampled, the deflection cosine μ_ℓ can be sampled uniformly.

4. DISCRETIZATION ALGORITHMS

The reactions discussed in Section 3 call for a proper discretization algorithm, capable of selecting the positions of the discretization points for both one and two-dimensional distributions, and therefore ensuring a correct interpolation up to a given tolerance, while minimizing the amount of stored data.

Starting with the simpler one-dimensional case, in this work we used two kind of algorithms.

- An additive algorithm, which starts only with the boundaries of the space to discretize. It recursively adds data points where the discretization is not precise enough. This requires exploring the behavior of the function by evaluating it at sample points that can then be added to the discretization if they bring new features that were not previously approximated. This algorithm is inspired from a routine used to discretize cross sections in the 'RECONR' module of the NJOY nuclear data processing system [6].
- The Douglas-Peucker subtractive algorithm [7], which starts with a set of points discretizing a

function, and tries to eliminate the redundant points while respecting the imposed tolerance.

To discretize a one-dimensional function, the additive algorithm is first used to explore the shape of the function and create a preliminary discretization. Then, the subtractive algorithm is used to remove any redundant points from the preliminary set, and obtain a more compact representation.

The two-dimensional discretized functions can be seen as an ensemble of distributions for different incident energies between which interpolation is performed. To discretize two-dimensional functions, we adapted the two algorithms mentioned above by having them add or remove entire distributions instead of single data points (the notion of ‘distance’ between distributions is generalized by using the uniform norm L_∞ , i.e. the largest distance between the two distributions). A two-dimensional additive algorithm is again used to obtain a preliminary discretization, which is then compressed by using the subtractive algorithm.

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

Due to the weight correction, adjoint simulations need both direct and adjoint nuclear data. Data were retrieved from the ENDF-B/VIII.0 library in the form of ACE files, processed with NJOY [6] and additionally parsed with the ALEXANDRIA module of TRIPOLI-5[®] [5]. We prepared adjoint cross sections and distribution laws for several nuclides relevant in reactor applications (¹H, ²H, ¹²C, ¹⁶O, ⁵⁶Fe, ²³⁵U, ²³⁸U, ²³⁹Pu), using the strategy presented in Section 3. Discretization tolerance for the adjoint data was set to $\pm 10\%$ for one-dimensional functions, and to $\pm 20\%$ for two-dimensional distributions. The resulting size of the prepared adjoint data is between 10 and 20 times smaller than the original nuclear data, which means that no significant increase in data library size is to be expected to run adjoint calculations. For illustration, a few relevant adjoint cross sections are shown in Figure 2.

A prototype Monte Carlo code was implemented to solve direct and adjoint continuous-energy transport problems in infinite media, sampling the adjoint collision event using Equation (5). A simple benchmark was used to test the validity of the adjoint sampling procedure. The simulation consists in a mixture of equal concentration of ²³⁸U and ¹H at 0 K. The adjoint source is a point at $E_{\min} = 0.1$ eV (corresponding to a point detector at the same energy), and the simulated energy range spans from E_{\min} to $E_{\max} = 20$ MeV. The collision importance ψ^\dagger is collected by 500 logarithmically-spaced bins that span the entire energy range. The simulation uses 10^5 particles grouped into 10^3 batches, and enforces population control (splitting and Russian roulette).

Figure 2. **Left.** The obtained adjoint cross sections for some reactions of ¹H and ²³⁸U using Equation (8). The resonances of elastic scattering of ²³⁸U are also visible in the adjoint cross section. **Right.** The collision importance ψ^\dagger and the statistical uncertainty (at 3 standard deviations) as a function of energy E , for a point detector placed at $E_{\min} = 0.1$ eV, in an infinite medium with the same concentration of ²³⁸U and ¹H, measured using 500 logarithmically-spaced energy bins ranging from $E_{\min} = 0.1$ eV to $E_{\max} = 20$ MeV.

The simulation results are provided in Figure 2. The collision importance ψ^\dagger , which is proportional

to the probability of a neutron scoring in the detector, has a local maximum at the detector energy. The impact of the absorption resonances of ^{238}U are clearly apparent in the dips of the importance at the corresponding energies. For each supplementary resonance that the neutron has to cross to get to the detector, the importance decreases, as the probability of the neutron surviving until reaching the detector decreases. At high energies ($E > 1$ MeV), the possible fission of ^{238}U increases the importance.

To test the validity of the adjoint sampling procedure and of the produced adjoint nuclear data, we evaluate a series of responses using ten different sources and ten different detectors (yielding 100 different responses), both with direct and adjoint Monte Carlo games. This requires 10 direct simulations and 10 adjoint simulations: we use 10^8 particles grouped in 10^4 batches for each calculation. The ten sources are uniformly distributed in ten logarithmically-spaced bins in the energy range $[0.1, 10]$ MeV. The ten detectors have uniform response functions in ten logarithmically-spaced bins in the energy range $[0.1, 10]$ eV. The reciprocity theorem states that, for a given source-detector pair, the direct and adjoint calculation must yield the same result (up to the stochastic uncertainty). The discrepancies between the adjoint and the direct estimates (normalized by the combined standard deviation) should follow a standard normal distribution, and were analyzed using the Student t -test. Out of the 100 responses compared, only 3 have discrepancies above two standard deviations, and none exceed three. A thorough statistical analysis will be conducted in a follow-up paper.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we described a strategy to prepare the adjoint cross sections and distribution laws necessary to sample the adjoint transport equation. In view of implementing such capability in TRIPOLI-5[®], we developed a simple adjoint Monte Carlo code to test the validity of the procedure in infinite media, continuous-energy problems using nuclear data from a modern nuclear data library.

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